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METHODS OF EFFECTIVE TEACHING OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN A SHORT PERIOD OF TIME IN FINLAND AND GREAT BRITAIN

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Abstract. Modern English Language teaching methods are considered in the article. Special attention is paid to the cross-cultural competence.

Keywords: English language, teaching writing, teaching reading, lexical and grammatical methods, computer technologies, cross-cultural competence.

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются современные методические приемы обучения английскому языку. Особое внимание уделяется формированию страноведческой компетенции.

Ключевые слова: английский язык, обучение письму, обучение чтению, лексикограмматический метод, компьютерные технологии, страноведческая компетенция.

The modern multicultural world is developing rapidly and intensively. Socio-economic and socio-political processes with a trend towards globalization and integration create certain conditions for the functioning of state and social systems. Scientific and technological progress entails a steady increase in the volume of new information. At present, the process of reforming the education system is underway in our country, and a competency-based approach is being actively applied. In such conditions, the issue of successful professional self-realization of the individual, the achievement of which is impossible without high-quality education in general and language education in particular, is of particular relevance. Therefore, in the country's higher educational institutions, the process of revising curricula and programs, introducing new methods and techniques for teaching a foreign language is underway [7, p.4-5].

Modern conditions of teaching and learning create a wide scope for the activities of the teacher in terms of the use of various technical innovations and devices, the amount of new information provides factual material for discussion and analysis.

Teachers of English today have the opportunity to visit the best language schools in English-speaking countries, undergo internships and training in them, which allows not only to improve their professional level and expand linguistic and regional competence, but also to exchange pedagogical and methodological work experience, borrow new methods of teaching English, aimed at to optimize the teaching process. One of these schools is Language Specialists International (Portsmouth, UK) [5].

Experienced school teachers (authors of textbooks, books, methodological systems and complexes) use effective methods of teaching English to foreigners. One of the directions of the school's work is preparing for certified exams in order to prepare for admission to higher educational institutions in the UK, Australia and a number of American universities (IELTS preparation). In the process of preparing for a multi-aspect international exam, students are taught to read, write, work with the lexical and grammatical component of language education. Teaching methods are varied, interesting, creative and dynamic. Their application is also possible in groups of students of various levels of training and professional orientation, incl. and non-linguistic specialties. Let's consider them in more detail.

IELTS preparation involves teaching the scientific style of writing, the final goal is writing a scientific abstract. The student does not receive an abstract writing algorithm at the beginning of the process, but independently goes through this step-by-step path under the strict guidance of the teacher. This type of work begins with what is called personalization (appeal to the personality of the student). That is, the development of certain rules, speech clichés, grammatical norms, etc. takes place on material that is not directly related to "serious" science. Students are offered to discuss topics that are close to them personally: hobbies, hobbies, music, cinema, etc. All discussions are held in mini-groups, in pairs, within the whole group, with a teacher. At the same time, students have the opportunity to share their opinions, ideas, enrich their vocabulary. The further scheme of work is as follows: Look out for interesting material (search for interesting material), Tailor the grammar to academic writing (grammar exercises), Write your own texts (writing your own text), Paragraph Reformulation (paragraph transformation using examples, introductory words etc.), Error Correction (work on errors), Turn dry tasks into interactive activities (using interactive activities), Model Answers (answers to questions according to the model), Peer Feedback (introspection), Make your own listening (listening). Thus, moving

from simple to complex, discussing various topics and expressing one's opinion, it is possible to achieve the set task [3, 4].

At the same time, accents are placed on the lexical and grammatical component of the language. At the same time, there is no clear division into vocabulary and grammar: these two aspects must coexist with each other. Taking into account this position, lexical and grammatical exercises are also compiled, aimed at consolidating the material covered. The development of new lexical units, phrases and phrases is carried out in parallel with the consolidation of the grammatical section [4].

IELTS preparation also includes learning to read and understand text. Not analytical reading with a detailed translation, but reading comprehension without painstaking work with a dictionary. In this case, it is possible to draw an analogy with the elements of introductory, search and viewing reading (these types of reading are widely used in teaching a foreign language to students of technical specialties). This type of work involves the following stages: Visual Dictogloss (visual familiarization with the text for a limited period of time), Wall reading (work in groups using motor activity), Crossing out words (crossing out unfamiliar words), Doing micro-skills with a very simple text (step-by-step work with plain text), Identifying topic sentences (defining a key sentence).

Moving from simple texts and their fragments to more complex ones, students learn to understand what they read, relying only on the vocabulary they know, learn to compare, analyze, select a title for the text and its part, determine key sentences, the main idea and purpose of the text, etc. And all this students discuss among themselves, with the teacher, analyze, ask questions. At the same time, the teacher tries as much as possible to interest students (and himself too!) Not only in content, but also in methods specially selected for each group, including using motor and physical activity (moving around the classroom of a student or group of students, leaving the office, working at boards, etc.). Each stage ends with a serious exam, according to the results of which students are transferred (or not transferred) to a group of a higher level [3, 4].

Today, there is no doubt that Web.2.0 has become an inexhaustible source of authentic materials that a teacher of foreign languages can use in their work. Resources with interactive games of various levels, sites for recording educational podcasts, wiki pages for group projects, various web quests and interactive exercises have taken a strong position in the methodological baggage of foreign language teachers.

Internet service such as Youtube deserves special attention. It is here that you can find an extensive collection of authentic materials in foreign languages, including English. Any teacher who confidently uses a computer and the Internet can upload video recordings of lessons, lectures, speeches at conferences, excerpts from favorite video works, but the quality of such recordings sometimes leaves much to be desired. From this point of view, video resources of English-language TV channels such as BBC 1, BBC 2, Channel 4 and others are of particular value.

Unfortunately, many high-quality films that are interesting both from a linguistic point of view and from the point of view of intercultural communication are not always available via Youtube outside of English-speaking countries. For example, watching the three-part film “All in the Best Possible Tastes with Grayson Perry” about the structure of modern society in England, which is available online on Channel 4, is not possible in Russia [1]. This 2012 documentary by acclaimed English artist Grayson Perry provides a modern, if somewhat subjective, look at the UK's traditional social stratification system. Only the trailer of the film is available on Youtube, a description of the content of each episode can be viewed on the channel's website. Nevertheless, Russian users can get acquainted with individual interviews with Grayson Perry, with trailers of several other films, with excerpts from programs with his participation, which can be used in classes in groups with different levels of student preparation, having developed a system of various exercises for the video.

The following types of exercises can be developed for working with a film, aimed at a detailed understanding of the content:

- a) multiple choice: choosing the correct answer;
- b) discussion of one's own choice in pairs, groups, with a teacher;
- c) lexical and grammatical tasks.

All exercises are focused on understanding the content of the viewed story and developing listening and speaking skills.

The teachers of the school actively use the relationship of culture and language in the process of working with foreign students. Leading experts in the field of methods of teaching foreign languages in our country also proclaim the principle of co-studying languages and cultures, which largely contributes to the successful formation of cultural and regional competence [2, 9]. This process is successful if it is based on authentic material that reflects the "model of culture and country studies" of the country of the

language being studied, extralinguistic information. The use of printed press materials, audio and video sequences, modern songs, films as a source of additional knowledge about the language in particular and society as a whole creates conditions for increasing students' motivation, expanding their linguistic and cultural horizons. Discussion of topical issues of a socio-political, cultural and public nature, a systematic presentation of country-specific material, the selection of which takes into account communicative and regional-specific interests - all this contributes to the effective formation of regional-specific competence. The success of language acquisition depends on the knowledge of the subject of communication: subject-thematic competence, and those methods on the basis of which the acquaintance with new linguistic and cultural material takes place [6, 8].

Thus, the complex application of these methodological techniques, relevant and interesting in their content, taking into account the individual characteristics of students creates the conditions for increasing the motivation of students, the effectiveness of the process of mastering the material. The experience of such internships, when the teacher finds himself on the other side of the classroom, is also useful from the point of view of assessing his teaching skills. This makes it possible to understand which teaching methods are the most productive, effective, interesting, to see how feasible the tasks offered to students are and to assess the degree of their own language proficiency as a means of communication.

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